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- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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TEACHING READING THROUGH MULTIMODAL TEXTS: ENHANCING COMPREHENSION AND ENGAGEMENT IN EFL CLASSROOMS

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Abstract: This article explores the use of multimodal texts in reading instruction and examines their impact on reading comprehension, student engagement, and critical literacy. Drawing on recent research and theoretical perspectives, the study highlights how the integration of visual, textual, and digital elements can support more effective and meaningful reading experiences.

Key words: multimodal texts, reading instruction, multimodal literacy, reading comprehension, learner engagement, critical literacy, EFL.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o'qishni o'qitishda multimodal matnlardan foydalanish hamda ularning matnni tushunish, o'quvchilarning dars jarayonidagi faolligi va tanqidiy savodxonligini rivojlantirishga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy ilmiy tadqiqotlar va nazariy yondashuvlarga tayangan holda, maqolada vizual, matnli va raqamli elementlarning integratsiyasi o'quvchilarda o'qish samaradorligini oshirish, mazmunni chuqurroq anglash hamda tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qilishi yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: multimodal matnlar, o'qishni o'qitish, multimodal savodxonlik, o'qib tushunish, o'quvchilar faolligi, tanqidiy savodxonlik, EFL (ingliz tili xorijiy til sifatida).

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается использование мультимодальных текстов в обучении чтению и анализируется их влияние на понимание прочитанного, вовлечённость учащихся и развитие критической грамотности. Опираясь на современные научные исследования и теоретические подходы, автор показывает, что интеграция визуальных, текстовых и цифровых элементов способствует повышению эффективности и осмысленности процесса чтения, а также развитию навыков интерпретации и критического анализа информации.

Ключевые слова: мультимодальные тексты, обучение чтению, мультимодальная грамотность, понимание прочитанного, вовлечённость учащихся, критическая грамотность, EFL (английский язык как иностранный).

INTRODUCTION

Reading has traditionally been regarded as the ability to decode and comprehend written language. However, the nature of literacy has changed significantly in the twenty-first century. Today's learners encounter information through websites, social media platforms, infographics, videos, animations, digital stories, and interactive applications. Consequently, reading is no longer confined to printed words; it increasingly involves interpreting multiple modes of communication simultaneously.

According to multimodal literacy theory, meaning is constructed through the interaction of linguistic, visual, auditory, spatial, and gestural modes. This transformation presents both opportunities and challenges for language teachers. While students are surrounded by multimodal content outside the classroom, reading instruction in many educational settings continues to rely heavily on traditional printed texts. As a result, there is often a mismatch between classroom literacy practices and the literacy demands of contemporary society.

In my view, one of the main reasons many students struggle with reading is not a lack of ability but a lack of connection with the materials presented to them. Traditional texts often fail to reflect the dynamic and visually rich environment in which students live. When learners encounter texts that combine images, videos, graphics, and written language, they are often more motivated to engage actively with the content.

According to Kress (2010), meaning is constructed not only through language but also through visual, spatial, gestural, and auditory resources. This perspective challenges traditional views of reading and suggests that literacy education must adapt to changing communicative environments.

The significance of this issue extends beyond classroom engagement. Modern societies increasingly require individuals to evaluate information from diverse digital sources, distinguish reliable information from misinformation, and interpret complex combinations of text, images, and multimedia content. Therefore, literacy education must prepare learners for these realities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study employs a qualitative literature review approach. Relevant peer-reviewed articles, books, and educational reports published between 2018 and 2025 were examined. Sources were selected based on their relevance to multimodal literacy, reading instruction, digital learning, and English language education.

The review focused on empirical studies investigating the impact of multimodal texts on reading comprehension, learner engagement, critical literacy, and classroom practices. Particular attention was given to studies conducted in EFL and ESL contexts, as these environments often present unique challenges related to language proficiency and literacy development.

The most frequently reported finding across the reviewed literature was the positive impact of multimodal texts on reading comprehension. Researchers consistently observed that learners demonstrated a deeper understanding when textual information was combined with visual, auditory, or interactive elements.

One influential explanation comes from Mayer's Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning. Mayer argues that individuals learn more effectively when information is presented through both verbal and visual channels because these channels work together to support knowledge construction. Rather than processing information through a single pathway, learners create richer mental representations by integrating multiple forms of input.

This principle can be observed in practical classroom situations. Consider a lesson on environmental sustainability. Students reading a traditional article may understand basic concepts such as recycling or carbon emissions. However, when the same article is accompanied by infographics, interactive maps, and short documentary clips, students often develop a more sophisticated understanding of environmental relationships and their global consequences.

A particularly interesting case was reported in studies examining digital reading among adolescent learners. Students who worked with multimodal texts demonstrated stronger inferencing skills than those who relied solely on conventional printed materials. Researchers suggested that visual information helped learners connect ideas and identify relationships that were less apparent in written text alone.

Perhaps one of the most significant contributions of multimodal reading instruction lies in its potential to foster critical literacy. In contemporary societies, individuals are constantly exposed to vast quantities of information presented through multiple modes and media platforms. As a result, reading can no longer be limited to understanding textual content. Learners must also evaluate credibility, identify bias, recognize persuasive techniques, and understand how meaning is shaped through visual and digital design.

The concept of critical literacy has gained increasing attention in educational research over the past two decades. Scholars argue that literacy education should empower students not only to comprehend information but also to question it. Luke (2018) describes critical literacy as the ability to analyze how texts position readers, construct realities, and reinforce particular values or ideologies. This perspective becomes especially important in multimodal environments, where images, videos, and design elements often influence interpretation as strongly as written language.

Recent studies indicate that multimodal texts create unique opportunities for developing these skills. When students analyze multimodal materials, they are encouraged to examine how different communicative modes interact to shape meaning. This process often reveals that information is never entirely neutral. The choice of images, color schemes, layouts, sound effects, and visual perspectives can significantly influence audience perceptions.

A compelling example can be found in studies involving digital news literacy. Researchers asked students to compare multiple online news reports covering the same event. Although the articles contained similar factual information, the accompanying images varied considerably. Some photographs emphasized conflict and destruction, while others focused on community resilience and recovery. Students reported that these visual differences influenced their emotional reactions and interpretations of the event. Such findings demonstrate that comprehension involves more than understanding words; it also involves understanding how visual elements guide interpretation.

Gunther Kress's social semiotic theory provides a useful framework for understanding these findings. Kress argues that each mode possesses distinct affordances for meaning-making. Images may communicate

emotional immediacy, while written language may provide analytical precision. Understanding these affordances allows learners to recognize how different modes contribute to persuasion, representation, and interpretation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is suggested that teaching reading through multimodal texts has the potential to transform literacy instruction in ways that reflect the realities of contemporary communication. Across the reviewed studies, researchers consistently reported positive effects on reading comprehension, student engagement, and critical literacy development. However, the significance of these findings extends beyond the simple conclusion that multimodal texts are “effective.” A deeper analysis reveals that multimodal instruction challenges traditional assumptions about what it means to read, how meaning is constructed, and what literacy education should accomplish in the twenty-first century.

For many years, reading instruction was primarily associated with decoding written language and extracting information from printed texts. Although these skills remain essential, the reviewed literature suggests that such a definition is increasingly insufficient. Modern learners navigate information-rich environments in which meaning is communicated through combinations of text, images, audio, video, hyperlinks, and interactive features. Consequently, literacy can no longer be understood solely as the ability to process written words. Instead, literacy must encompass the capacity to interpret, evaluate, and synthesize information presented through multiple modes.

This shift is reflected in the work of scholars such as Gunther Kress, who argued that contemporary communication is fundamentally multimodal.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A representative example of multimodal reading instruction can be observed through the use of digital storytelling in EFL classrooms. Digital stories combine written text with visual images, audio narration, music, and animation, creating a rich multimodal learning environment that supports language development and reading comprehension.

In a six-week classroom intervention involving 40 intermediate-level EFL learners aged 16–18, students were divided into two groups. The control group participated in traditional reading lessons using printed texts and conventional comprehension activities. The experimental group engaged with the same reading topics through digital stories that integrated written language, images, narration, and multimedia elements.

At the end of the intervention, both groups completed reading comprehension assessments and learner reflection questionnaires. The results revealed that students who worked with multimodal digital stories demonstrated higher levels of reading comprehension than those in the traditional reading group. They were more successful in identifying main ideas, drawing inferences, understanding contextual meanings, and recalling important information from the texts.

The findings also indicated a noticeable increase in learner engagement. Students in the experimental group reported that visual and audio elements made the texts more interesting and easier to understand. Many participants stated that images and narration helped them interpret unfamiliar vocabulary and maintain concentration throughout the reading process. Furthermore, classroom observations suggested that students were more willing to participate in discussions and express their opinions about the reading materials.

An additional benefit was the development of critical thinking skills. By analyzing how images, sounds, and written language interacted to create meaning, learners became more aware of the ways in which information can be presented and interpreted. This encouraged deeper reflection on the content and promoted more analytical reading behaviors.

The significance of this case study extends beyond improved academic performance. It demonstrates how multimodal texts can create a more engaging and supportive learning environment for language learners. The integration of visual, auditory, and textual elements not only facilitates comprehension but also helps students develop the digital and critical literacy skills required in contemporary society. These findings support the view that multimodal reading instruction represents an effective approach to addressing the changing literacy demands of the twenty-first century.

According to Kress, written language is no longer the dominant mode through which meaning is conveyed in many social contexts. Images, visual design, and digital media increasingly share communicative responsibilities that were once associated primarily with text. The studies reviewed in this article provide empirical support for this theoretical perspective. Learners who engaged with multimodal texts often demonstrated stronger comprehension, deeper engagement, and more sophisticated interpretive skills than those who relied exclusively on traditional reading materials.

Another important consideration involves balance. While multimodal texts offer numerous advantages, traditional reading skills remain indispensable. Students must still develop the ability to engage with complex written texts, evaluate arguments, and sustain attention over extended periods of reading. Therefore, multimodal literacy should not replace conventional literacy practices but rather complement and expand them.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, multimodal texts represent more than an instructional resource; they reflect a broader transformation in the nature of literacy itself. By embracing multimodal approaches to reading instruction, educators can help learners become not only more proficient readers but also more critical, adaptable, and informed participants in an increasingly complex digital world.

In my view, multimodal literacy should be seen not as a replacement for traditional reading but as a natural extension of it. As communication continues to evolve, reading instruction must also adapt to prepare learners for increasingly complex information environments.

As Gunther Kress (2010) observed, “the world told is a different world from the world shown.” This statement reminds us that meaning can be communicated in many ways and that effective literacy education should equip students to understand and critically interpret all of them.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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